

Tl(III) Oxidation of Lactic Acid Catalysed by Manganous Ions

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Tl(III) oxidation of lactic acid, catalysed by manganous ions in aqueous acetic acid, has been found to induce the polymerization of methyl methacrylate showing the intervention of organic free radical of the type HOCHR. The observation indicates that Tl(III) reacts as one electron oxidant in the oxidation of lactic acid with intermediate formation of Tl(II). The catalytic function may be ascribed to equilibria, $Tl(III) + Mn(II)L \rightleftharpoons Tl(II) + Mn(III)L$ in which the lactic acid functions as a ligand. The reaction with respect to each, oxidant as well as organic substrate has been found to obey first order kinetics. Thallic acetate has been shown to be the active oxidant in aqueous acetic acid medium.

The values of thermodynamic parameters, viz. entropy of activation, heat of activation, free energy of activation, energy of activation and frequency factor have been evaluated as, $\Delta S = 23.33$ e.u., $\Delta H = 30.1$ K cal/mol, $\Delta F = 23.0$ K cal/mol., $\Delta E = 30.84$ K cal/mol and $PZ = 8.35 \times 10^{17} \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively.

A mechanism is proposed to account for the observed stoichiometry, kinetic parameters and other experimental observations.

Tl(III) unlike most metal ions¹⁻⁹ behaves as two electron oxidant¹⁰⁻¹⁶. In fact the information available on the mode of oxidation involving Tl(III) is inadequate.

It has been reported recently¹⁷ that the radiation induced oxidation of alcohols by Tl(III) in acid aqueous solution proceeds via the intermediate formation of Tl(II) by a mechanism involving both Tl(II) and organic free radical.

However this paper describes the interesting results in Tl(III) oxidation of lactic acid, catalysed by manganous ions in aqueous acetic acid medium which are not reported in the literature.

Experimental

Materials: Thallium(III) acetate was prepared according to the method given by Henry¹⁵. Lactic acid and glacial acetic acid were of Analar B.D.H. grade. Triple distilled water was used throughout the course of investigation. All other chemicals used were of either Analar or pure reagent grade.

Kinetic Measurements: The reactants and the catalyst solutions of requisite concentration (in a fixed composition of acetic acid water mixture (v/v)), were brought to the desired thermostat temperature and then rapidly mixed in bottle previously brought to the thermostat temperature. The Tl(III) acetate

was added last. The kinetics of the reaction were followed by estimating unreacted Tl(III) at various time intervals by an iodometric procedure¹⁵ against standard thiosulphate and using freshly prepared starch as an indicator.

Stoichiometry and Product Analysis: Stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by taking the substrate in excess as well as by taking the oxidant in excess. The former to judge the reaction steps during kinetic runs and latter to judge the overall oxidation products.

(a) It was observed that when the organic substrate was in excess, all the Tl(III) was reduced to Tl(I) with the formation of same number of moles of acetaldehyde.

The stoichiometric studies between lactic acid and Tl(III) indicate 1 : 1 mole ratio under the said conditions. The formation of acetaldehyde was confirmed during the course of the reaction by preparing its 2 : 4 dinitrophenyl hydrazone of acetaldehyde, the M.P. was found to be 169°.

Thus the reaction under the conditions of kinetic run can be represented as—

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(b) In order to study the overall oxidation product, thallic perchlorate was taken in place of thallic acetate. This is to facilitate the identification of ultimate oxidation products easily, because the presence of acetic acid would give difficulty in qualitative analysis of organic products. Thallic perchlorate was prepared by simply dissolving thallic oxide in perchloric acid of desired strength and Tl(III) was estimated iodometrically.

The reaction mixture containing known excess of thallic perchlorate in perchloric acid over organic substrate was kept at 70° for about twelve hours. The unused oxidant was estimated iodometrically. Acetic acid was found to be the ultimate oxidation product. It was identified by preparing its S. benzyl thiouronium compound¹⁸. The M. P. was found to be 137.2.

The experimental result ($\Delta \text{Tl(III)}/\Delta \text{org.substrate}$) lead to the following equation—

Test for Organic free radical: The reaction mixture was flushed with nitrogen to expel oxygen from the system, before the addition of methyl methacrylate. The on-set of polymerisation was indicated by the appearance of turbidity in the initially clear solution. The turbidity increased with the progress of polymerization. This indicated the presence of organic free radical of the type HO CHR which intervenes in the oxidation process⁷.

Test for Carbon Dioxide: Formation of CO₂ was detected by carefully carrying out the reaction in a closed test-tube carrying a small bent tube dipping in baryta water.

Results and Discussion

Tl(III) oxidation of lactic acid (LA) has been studied in detail and the results of the kinetic experiments in 16.6% (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture at the 0.044M manganous ions concentration are presented in Table 1. The reactions were carried out under pseudo first order conditions taking organic substrate always in excess.

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [Tl(III)] AND [LA] AT 60°C, SOLVENT=16.6% WATER HOAC (v/v); 10⁴[Mn²⁺]=4.40M

[Tl(III)] × 10 ³ M	[LA] M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹
3.0	1.66	6.648 ± 0.18
3.0	1.33	5.442 ± 0.12
3.0	1.00	3.845 ± 0.16
3.0	0.80	3.705 ± 0.15
2.6	1.66	6.705 ± 0.06
2.2	1.66	6.687 ± 0.05
2.0	1.66	6.707 ± 0.07

It was observed that the rate of oxidation in the given range of concentration were found to proceed satisfactorily at measurable rate, but becomes kinetically immeasurable if attempt is made to increase or decrease this concentration range of either oxidant or organic substrate.

The reactions exhibit a total second order, first order each with respect to Tl(III) and lactic acid concentrations. Any particular run has been found to give linear plots for about 75% of the reaction. The duplicate rate measurements were found to be reproducible to ± 2%. The values of pseudo first order rate constants at different temperatures along with thermodynamic parameters are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON REACTION RATE 10⁴[Tl(III)]=3.0M; [LA]=1.65M; 10⁴[Mn²⁺]=4.40M. SOLVENT=16.6% WATER HOAC(v/v)

Temp. A°	10 ⁴ k ₁ (min ⁻¹)	ΔS (e.u)	PZ × 10 ⁻⁷ (min ⁻¹)	ΔH (K cal/mol)	ΔF (K cal/mol)	ΔE (K cal/mol)
328	3.978 ± 0.11	23.84	10.23	30.1	23.0	
333	6.648 ± 0.18	23.46	8.64	30.1	23.1	30.8
						(mean)
338	8.696 ± 0.10	22.58	5.61	30.1	23.2	
343	2.696 ± 0.12	23.47	8.93	30.1	22.7	

The activation energy coupled with entropy of activation together play a vital role in determining the rate and reactivity of the reaction.

The results indicate that the rate of reaction is greatly changed by the change of temperature, such reactions have high activation energy and slow in nature. This fact is further supported by the observed values of free energy and heat of activation.

In fact the values of ΔE, ΔH and ΔF indicate that the reaction rate ought to be immeasurably slow, but the recorded values of entropy of activation and frequency factor make the reaction rate kinetically measurable.

Effect of Manganous Ion Concentration on Reaction Rate:

In order to study the effect of manganous ions on reaction rate, the different concentrations of manganous sulphate were prepared in 0.33 N sulphuric acid (in which manganous ions were found to remain fairly stable for much longer period).

The sulphate ions have been found to have no effect on rate constants. The experimental results are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON MANGANOUS IONS CONCENTRATION

$10^3[\text{Tl(III)}]=3.0M$; $[\text{LA}]=1.66M$;
Solvent=16.6% water HOAC; Temp.=60°C

$10^3[\text{Mn}^{++}]M$	16.6	4.4	2.2
$10^4k_1(\text{min}^{-1})$	12.22 ± 0.34	6.65 ± 0.18	3.31 ± 0.11

Effect of Solvent Composition on Rate Constant :

The results recorded in Table 4, show that the values of rate constants increase on increasing the % composition of acetic acid.

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON SOLVENT COMPOSITION

$10^3[\text{Tl(III)}]=3.0M$; $[\text{LA}]=1.66M$;
 $10^3[\text{Mn}^{++}]=4.40M$; Temp.=60°C

% of water HOAC (v/v)	16.6	20.0	25.0	33.3
$10^4k_1(\text{min}^{-1})$	6.65 ± 0.18	7.55 ± 0.14	9.27 ± 0.09	10.70 ± 0.1

This observation is similar to the observation recorded by Bakore, et al¹⁹, Srinivasan et al¹⁸, and Mohanty et al²⁰, in the oxidation of ethyl glycolate by chromic acid, and Tl(III) oxidation of alcohols, mandelic acid, atrolactic acid, benzillic acid, etc., respectively. This may be attributed that, the increase in the acetic acid composition, decreases the dielectric constant of the solvent²¹, and increase the protonation in the oxidising species which lead to increased rate of oxidation.

Effect of Salts on Rate Constant :

Addition of either sodium bisulphate, sodium sulphate or sodium chloride have been found to exert no effect on the oxidation rate, therefore it was not felt necessary to keep the ionic strength constant. Thus in the present investigation the formation of species like $\text{Tl(OAc)}_2\text{Cl}$, or $\text{Tl(OAc)(HSO}_4^-)_2$ may be easily ruled out.

The retarding effect on rate constant has been observed by the addition of salt sodium acetate. It may be due to the formation of less reactive species like Tl(OAc)_2^- as also pointed out by Mohanty et al²⁰ and Srinivasan et al¹⁸.

Nature of Tl(III) Species :

Since the oxidation has been carried out in aqueous acetic acid medium, the following species of Tl(III) may be expected to be involved in the oxidation process.

- | | |
|---|---------------------------------|
| (1) $\text{Tl}^+(\text{OAc})_2\text{OAc}^-$ | (2) $\text{Tl}_2(\text{OAc})_4$ |
| (3) Tl(OAc)_2^- | (4) $\text{Tl(OH}^{++})$ |
| (5) Tl(OAc)_2^+ | (6) Tl(OAc)_3 |

The ion pair $\text{Tl}^+(\text{OAc})_2\text{OAc}^-$ and the double salt $\text{Tl}_2(\text{OAc})_4$ have been shown¹⁸ to have insignificant role in redox-reaction in acetic acid medium.

The rate of reaction is found to be retarded by the addition of sodium acetate ; it may be due to the formation less reactive species of Tl(OAc)_2^- . Srinivasan et al¹⁸ have shown that the addition of sodium acetate of higher concentration altogether stops the reaction. So this cannot be considered as reactive species.

$\text{Tl(OH}^{++})$ is the hydrolytic species of thallium salt, this occurs when the acid concentration is insufficient to stop the hydrolysis. It has been reported¹¹ that in acid concentration of 3.13 M, the hydrolysis is negligible. It means that under the existing condition the hydrolysis of thallic salt is almost negligible. So the possibility of formation of $\text{Tl(OH}^{++})$ species may also be ruled out.

The experimental observation has shown that increase in protonation leads to the formation of Tl(OAc)_2^+ species. This species is dominating in higher acid concentration range.

For all the kinetic runs the concentration of the acid chosen is just sufficient to stop the hydrolysis of thallic salt. It means that the active species involved in the present investigation under the existing condition is Tl(OAc)_3 .

The existence of this species is also reported by many authors^{18,19,22,23}.

Reaction Mechanism :

Tl(III) appears to have no tendency to induce polymerization as indicated in the redox system of Tl(III) with different organic substrates^{11,13-15}.

The redox potential of Tl(III)/Tl(I) ($E_0=1.25\text{ v}$) and Mn(III)/Mn(II) ($E_0=1.5\text{ v}$) couple clearly show that Tl(III) as such would be incapable of oxidising Mn(II).

The catalytic activity evidently depends on the fact that lactic acid complexes with manganous ion in which redox potential of $[\text{Mn(III)}-(\text{LA})]/[\text{Mn(II)}-(\text{LA})]$ becomes sufficiently low so as to allow the formation of $[\text{Mn(III)}-(\text{LA})]$ by the oxidation with Tl(III), which leads to one electron change ; that is the formation of Tl(II) is evident. However all the attempts to detect Mn(III) and Tl(II) were met with failure because of their fast breakdown.

Thus the slow oxidation process may involve the transfer of an electron to Tl(III) from a complex compound of manganese(II), followed by a much faster breakdown of manganese(III) complex. Similar single electron transfer process from a

manganese(II) complex have also been suggested in the oxidation of malonic acid by quinquevalent vanadium catalysed by manganous ions²⁴.

Thus the following reaction scheme seems to accord with the experimental results reported.

The $k_2 \gg k_1$ and steady state concentration of the species Mn(III)L is very small.

$$\frac{-d[\text{TI(III)}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1[\text{Mn(II)L}][\text{TI(III)}]}{1 + \frac{k_{-1}}{k_2}[\text{TI(II)}]}$$

$$\frac{-d[\text{TI(III)}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{Mn(II)L}][\text{TI(III)}]$$

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